

Exponential Corrections to Ramanujan's Second Formula for the Ellipse Perimeter: A Set of Ultra-Accurate Closed-Form Formulas

Salvador E. Ayala-Raggi^{*1} and Manuel Rendón-Marín^{†1}

¹Facultad de Ciencias de la Electrónica, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla (BUAP), Puebla, México

Ver.2.0 - April 2026

This work is an extended and significantly expanded version of our previously published article: Ayala-Raggi, S.E.; Rendón-Marín, M. An Exponential Correction to Ramanujan's Second Formula for Ellipse Perimeter Computation. *AppliedMath* 2026, 6, 56. <https://doi.org/10.3390/appliedmath6040056>.

Abstract

The exact perimeter of an ellipse involves the complete elliptic integral of the second kind, which lacks a closed-form expression in elementary functions. As a result, analytical approximations have been widely studied for applications requiring fast and accurate evaluation of elliptical geometries. In this work, we present an extended framework of exponential corrections to Ramanujan's second formula, building upon our previously published results. The proposed approach introduces a new family of ultra-accurate and compact closed-form approximations, including multi-exponential models with enhanced flexibility. The resulting formulas preserve simplicity while achieving maximum relative errors ranging from 0.57 down to 0.02 ppm over the full eccentricity range. This represents a substantial improvement over classical and modern approximations, while maintaining low computational cost and single-line analytical structure. Due to their robustness, quasi-exact behavior at both circular and highly eccentric limits, and suitability for numerical algorithms and embedded implementations, the proposed approximations are particularly attractive for engineering applications involving elliptical geometries.

Keywords: closed-form ellipse perimeter approximation; Ramanujan II approximation to ellipse perimeter; perimeter of the elliptical orbit of comets; approximation to ellipse circumference

1 Introduction

The computation of the perimeter of an ellipse is a classical problem in mathematics that has attracted attention for centuries. Unlike the circumference of a circle, which is solved by a simple closed-form expression as $P = 2\pi r$, the perimeter of an ellipse with semi-axes a and b cannot be expressed as an elementary function. Instead, the exact solution involves the complete elliptic integral of the second kind. Although this expression is mathematically exact, it is computationally more expensive than a compact closed-form expression. Specifically, in practical applications this computational cost becomes important when the calculation has to be performed repeatedly, sometimes thousands of times, and a "faster formula" is evidently more convenient. For this reason, numerous analytical approximations have been proposed throughout the history of mathematics, seeking a balance between simplicity and accuracy. The challenge lies in designing compact closed-form expressions that remain highly accurate over the full range of ellipse eccentricities. In this paper, we address this challenge by proposing our exponential correction to the well known Ramanujan's second formula.

Some current practical applications in engineering and numerical contexts where the computation of the ellipse perimeter is required are the following: In electromagnetic engineering, explicit perimeter formulas are used in the design and miniaturization of elliptical microstrip patch antennas (1). In vibration-assisted machining, the perimeter of an elliptical tool trajectory is used to relate the cutting

^{*}Corresponding author: salvador.raggi@correo.buap.mx

[†]manuel.rendon@correo.buap.mx

speed, the duty cycle, and the efficiency of the process (2). In composite materials engineering, the perimeter of the ellipse appears in the homogenization of the multi-physical properties of fibers with non-circular cross sections, commonly evaluated using Ramanujan-type approximations (3). Thermal modeling based on the finite element method also requires accurate estimates of the perimeter of ellipses when anatomical segments are approximated by elliptical geometries (4). Overall, the balance of simplicity, stability, and sub-ppm accuracy makes the proposed approximation in this paper attractive for practical engineering and technological computations.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the historical development of analytical approximations for the perimeter of the ellipse. Section 3 describes the methodology used to derive the proposed exponential corrections to Ramanujan’s second approximation. Section 4 presents numerical experiments and comparative error analyzes with classical and modern formulas. Section 5 discusses the results and highlights the advantages of the proposed approach, and finally Section 6 summarizes the main conclusions.

2 Historical Overview and Related Work

The exact computation of the perimeter of an ellipse has been a classical problem in mathematics since antiquity. Unlike the circumference of a circle, which admits a closed-form expression $P = 2\pi r$, the ellipse with the major semi-axis a and the minor semi-axis b ($a \geq b$) does not have a simple algebraic expression for its perimeter. Instead, the exact formula involves the complete elliptic integral of the second kind, $E(e)$, where e is the eccentricity, i.e.,

$$P_{exact} = 4a E(e), \quad \text{and} \quad E(e) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad , \quad e = \sqrt{1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2}}. \quad (1)$$

Because elliptic integrals resisted closed-form evaluation for centuries, mathematicians and scientists proposed numerous approximations, balancing simplicity with accuracy. We summarize seven formulas of historical and practical importance.

2.1 Arithmetic and Geometric Mean Approximations to the Ellipse Perimeter

Historically, astronomy has been the science that has motivated the study of ellipses and their perimeter. This is because the orbits of all celestial bodies are elliptical. There are two approaches to the perimeter of the ellipse based on Kepler’s ideas (1609) (5), which take as the perimeter of the ellipse that which corresponds to that of a circle whose radius is the arithmetic or geometric mean of the two radii of the ellipse. One of them is the arithmetic mean of the ellipse semi-axes, and the other corresponds to the geometric mean of these semi-axes (7; 6):

$$P_{AM} = \pi(a + b). \quad (2)$$

$$P_{GM} = 2\pi\sqrt{ab}. \quad (3)$$

Although exact for the circle ($a = b$), these formulas become increasingly inaccurate for ellipses with a large eccentricity.

2.2 Peano’s Formula

Giuseppe Peano (1889) introduced an expression to approximate the ellipse perimeter (8), which is a weighted average between geometric and arithmetic means attributed to Kepler:

$$P_{Peano} = \pi \left(3 \frac{a + b}{2} - \sqrt{ab} \right). \quad (4)$$

This expression is a linear combination of both means (arithmetic and geometric) resulting in a more precise approximation than each of them taken individually for low eccentricities.

2.3 Euler's Formula

Leonhard Euler (1773) improved on this by considering the quadratic mean of the semi-axes (9; 7), which is also the first term of his famous series, giving the following:

$$P_{Euler} = 2\pi\sqrt{\frac{a^2+b^2}{2}}. \quad (5)$$

This expression is significantly more accurate than Peano's but still yields large errors for highly elongated ellipses.

2.4 Euler-Ivory's Series Expansion

The classical expansion in infinite series of the elliptic integral proposed by Euler in 1773 (9) in terms of n is

$$AMB = \frac{c\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot 4} n^2 - \frac{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8} n^4 - \frac{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 9}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdot 8 \cdot 10 \cdot 12} n^6 - \dots \right\}$$

where $n = \frac{a^2-b^2}{a^2+b^2}$ is an eccentricity measure, $c = \sqrt{a^2+b^2}$ and AMB represents the quarter of the elliptical arc, measured from the vertex A (end of the major semi-axis) to vertex B (end of the minor semi-axis) passing through the midpoint M of the said arc.

To accelerate convergence, it was rewritten in terms of h by Ivory in 1825 (10), although it is also known as Gauss-Kummer series of h :

$$P_{Euler-Ivory} = \pi(a+b) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[\binom{\frac{1}{2}}{n} \right]^2 h^n = \pi(a+b) \left[1 + \frac{h}{4} + \frac{h^2}{64} + \frac{h^3}{256} + \dots \right]. \quad (6)$$

Here h is a kind of eccentricity that takes values from $h = 0$ for the circle to $h = 1$ for the completely elongated ellipse defined as

$$h = \left(\frac{a-b}{a+b} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

2.5 Ramanujan I

In the early 20th century, Srinivasa Ramanujan proposed remarkably accurate approximations (11; 7). His first formula ($R1$) is

$$P_{R1} = \pi \left[3(a+b) - \sqrt{(3a+b)(a+3b)} \right]. \quad (8)$$

This compact formula remains widely cited due to its balance of simplicity and improved accuracy.

2.6 Ramanujan II

Ramanujan also proposed, in terms of h (see Equation (7)), a second even more precise expression ($R2$) (11; 7):

$$P_{R2} = \pi(a+b) \left(1 + \frac{3h}{10 + \sqrt{4-3h}} \right). \quad (9)$$

This approximation achieves errors close to 4×10^{-4} or less across a wide range of axis ratios.

2.7 Ramanujan-Cantrell's Formula

Building upon Ramanujan II, Cantrell (2004) (7) introduced an additional corrective term to further reduce the error:

$$P_{Cantrell} = \pi(a+b) \left(1 + \frac{3h}{10 + \sqrt{4-3h}} + ch^{12} \right), \quad \text{where } c = \frac{4}{\pi} - \frac{14}{11}. \quad (10)$$

This modification reduces the maximum relative error to about 1.4×10^{-5} , representing one of the best-known simple closed-form approximations.

2.8 Koshy's Formulas for Quarter-Perimeter

More recently, Koshy (2024) proposed two formulas for the quarter-perimeter (12), denoted $Q(a, b)$. The first formula, more accurate than the second one, is of the form

$$Q(a, b) \approx Q(a, b; p) = (a^p + b^p)^{1/p}, \quad (11)$$

$$\text{where } p = p(a, b; k) = \frac{\ln(2)}{\ln(\pi/2)} + 1 - (b/a)^k,$$

and $k = 0.03214 - 0.0734(b/a) + 0.0863(b/a)^2 - 0.0681(b/a)^3 + 0.02306(b/a)^4$. Finally, the perimeter can be calculated as $P_{Koshy1} \approx 4Q(a, b)$. This approach yields a maximum error close to 8.7 ppm. The second formula proposed by Koshy is:

$$Q(a, b) \approx Q(a, b; 2, k) = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} + \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \sqrt{2}\right) \left(\frac{GM}{AM}\right)^k \sqrt{ab}, \quad (12)$$

where $k = 2.6071 + 1.2243\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) - 1.2673\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^2 + 0.45566\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^3$, $AM = \frac{a+b}{2}$, and $GM = \sqrt{ab}$.

2.9 Recent Approaches

There are other recent works, like the one proposed by Moscato in (13), giving a maximum absolute relative error of 2.7 ppm. In an effort to provide the most complete overview possible, we must mention that there are some recent approaches such as a Sykora's optimization based on Ahmadi's proposal in (14), that achieve very low error (< 1 ppm); however, we must point out that these are reported in web compilations, and we are not aware of them having been published in peer-reviewed sources. Finally, A recent work by Mamoun (17) proposes a highly accurate framework based on a continued-fraction interpretation of Ramanujan's second formula combined with multi-exponential and logarithmic corrections. While this approach achieves sub-parts-per-billion accuracy, it involves a substantial increase in structural complexity. In contrast, the present work emphasizes compact closed-form expressions with significantly fewer terms, achieving sub-ppm accuracy while preserving simplicity and practical usability.

2.10 Error Analysis for Extreme Ratios of a/b

To understand the behavior of classical approximation formulas historically proposed for the perimeter of the ellipse, it is instructive to analyze their limiting behavior for extreme aspect ratios a/b . Two limits are particularly informative:

$$\frac{a}{b} \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{a}{b} \rightarrow \infty.$$

When $a = b$, the ellipse becomes a circle and, therefore, remembering that $P_{exact} = P_{exact}(a, b)$ (see Equation (1)) denotes the exact perimeter of an ellipse,

$$P_{exact}(a, a) = 2\pi a.$$

On the other hand, as $b \rightarrow 0^+$ with a fixed, the ellipse degenerates into a line segment of length $2a$ and its perimeter tends to

$$P_{exact}(a, b) \rightarrow 4a.$$

The limiting relative error of any approximation $P^*(a, b)$ is defined as

$$\varepsilon(P^*) = \frac{P^*(a, b) - P_{exact}(a, b)}{P_{exact}(a, b)}. \quad (13)$$

Table 1 summarizes the limiting behavior of the classical formulas for the two extreme ratios of a/b .

Table 1: Limiting behavior of classical and modern ellipse perimeter approximations for the two extreme cases $a/b \rightarrow 1$ and $a/b \rightarrow \infty$. The last column reports the limiting relative error in parts per million (ppm), defined as $10^6 \varepsilon$ with $P_{exact}(a, b) \rightarrow 4a$ when $a/b \rightarrow \infty$.

Method	$\lim_{a/b \rightarrow 1} \frac{P^*}{a}$	$\lim_{a/b \rightarrow \infty} \frac{P^*}{a}$	$ \varepsilon_\infty $ (ppm)
Geometric mean (1609)	2π	0	1,000,000
Arithmetic mean (1609)	2π	π	214,602
Euler (1774)	2π	$\sqrt{2}\pi$	110,721
Peano (1889)	2π	$\frac{3\pi}{2}$	178,097
Ramanujan I (1914)	2π	$(3 - \sqrt{3})\pi$	4155.03
Ramanujan II (1914)	2π	$\frac{14\pi}{11}$	402.337
Cantrell (2004)	2π	$\frac{11}{4}$	0
R2/2exp (reference proposed in this work)	$2\pi(1 + 2.86 \times 10^{-17})$	$\frac{\frac{14\pi}{11}}{1 - (A + C)} \approx 3.99999999992$	1.94×10^{-4}

3 Methodology

3.1 Numerical Computation of the Exact Elliptic Integral

In this work, the reference perimeter, P , used for the error evaluation was computed numerically using the ellipsis function `ellipe` from the Python library `mpmath`; P is the best numerical approximation to P_{exact} . This library implements arbitrary-precision floating-point arithmetic and provides efficient algorithms for evaluating special functions, including elliptic integrals.

In the present computations, the default working precision of the library was used, which corresponds to approximately 15 decimal digits, which is comparable to standard double-precision arithmetic. The results reported in this paper are completely reliable because they are of the order of 10^{-7} , whereas the numeric precision is of the order of 10^{-15} , i.e., several orders of magnitude smaller.

3.2 One-Exponential Heuristic Correction to R_2 ($R_2/1exp$)

We started by studying the relative error curve of the classical second Ramanujan formula P_{R_2} given in Equation (9). From now on, for all formulas, the relative error will be calculated using Equation (13), where P_{exact} is replaced by P , and P^* any perimeter approximation formula. Using Equation (13), the relative error of P_{R_2} is $\varepsilon(P_{R_2})$. We have seen that $\varepsilon(P_{R_2})$ expressed as a function of h , is smooth, negative, and increases in magnitude as $h \rightarrow 1$ (high eccentricity), resembling a decaying exponential in $1 - h$ of the form $\Delta\varepsilon = -Ae^{-B(1-h)}$. Therefore, if we start from the hypothesis that there must exist $\Delta\varepsilon$ such that $\varepsilon(P_{R_2}) - \Delta\varepsilon = 0$, then substituting $\varepsilon(P^*)$ in Equation (13) by $\Delta\varepsilon$ results in

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{P_{R_2} - P}{P}. \quad (14)$$

if and only if

$$P = \frac{P_{R_2}}{1 + \Delta\varepsilon}. \quad (15)$$

By substituting $\Delta\varepsilon$ with $-Ae^{-B(1-h)}$ in Equation (15), we obtain a better approximation to P than P_{R_2} . Therefore, we define

$$P_1 = \frac{P_{R_2}}{1 - Ae^{-B(1-h)}}, \quad (16)$$

where P has been replaced by P_1 .

The parameters (A, B) are fitted once (and reused universally) by minimizing a uniform error criterion over a mesh (see Algorithm 1). Specifically, we minimize the maximum absolute relative error.

$$\Phi(A, B) = \max_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{D}_1} |\varepsilon(a, b)|, \quad \mathcal{D}_1 = \{b = 1, a \in [1, 100]\}. \quad (17)$$

We used a numerical minimax optimization procedure (15). The minor semi-axis was fixed at $b = 1$ and the major semi-axis a was varied over a dense grid of 3000 uniformly distributed values.

The optimization seeks the set of parameters that minimizes the maximum relative error over the entire range of ellipse shapes considered. This minimax criterion ensures that the approximation remains uniformly accurate across the whole domain rather than optimizing only the average error.

In this way, we obtain the following

$$A = 3.62077 \times 10^{-4}, \quad B = 10.826,$$

which yields a maximum relative error of about 2.14 ppm on \mathcal{D}_1 (see Figure 1a). Equation (16) can be reliably used for $a \leq 100$. An attempt was made to perform the same fitting of these constants in a wider range (from $a = 1$ to $a = 1000$) and the maximum relative error increased to 6 ppm, so it was decided to limit the range from $a = 1$ to $a = 100$. In an interesting fact, in this interval there are all the elliptical orbits of all known comets.

Algorithm 1 Minimax fitting of corrected Ramanujan II ellipse-perimeter approximations

Require: fixed $b > 0$, interval $[a_{\min}, a_{\max}]$, number of grid points N , model type $M \in \{1\text{Exp}, 2\text{Exp}\}$

Ensure: optimal parameters and maximum relative error

1: Construct the grid

$$a_i = a_{\min} + \frac{i-1}{N-1}(a_{\max} - a_{\min}), \quad i = 1, \dots, N$$

2: **for** $i = 1, \dots, N$ **do**

3: Compute

$$h_i = \left(\frac{a_i - b}{a_i + b} \right)^2, \quad t_i = 1 - h_i$$

4: Compute the numerical approximation to the exact perimeter

$$P(a_i, b) = 4a_i E \left(1 - \left(\frac{b}{a_i} \right)^2 \right)$$

5: Compute Ramanujan II approximation

$$PR2(a_i, b) = \pi(a_i + b) \left(1 + \frac{3h_i}{10 + \sqrt{4 - 3h_i}} \right)$$

6: **end for**

7: **if** $M = 1\text{Exp}$ **then**

8: Define

$$P^*(a, b) = \frac{PR2(a, b)}{1 - Ae^{-B(t_i)}}$$

9: **else**

10: Impose $A + C = S$, set $A = S - C$

11: Define

$$P^*(a, b) = \frac{PR2(a, b)}{1 - [(S - C)e^{-B(t_i)} + Ce^{-D(t_i)}]}$$

12: **end if**

13: Define minimax objective

$$\Phi(\theta) = \max_i \frac{|P^*(a_i, b; \theta) - P(a_i, b)|}{P(a_i, b)}$$

14: Initialize a population of candidate parameters θ_j . Being $\theta_j = \{A, B\}$ when $M = 1\text{Exp}$ or $\theta_j = \{C, B, D\}$ when $M = 2\text{Exp}$.

15: **repeat**

16: **for** each candidate θ_j **do**

17: Generate trial parameters by mutation and recombination

18: Evaluate $\Phi(\theta_j)$

19: Select the candidate with smaller objective value

20: **end for**

21: **until** convergence of the population

22: Refine the best candidate using a local optimization method. Specifically Powell's method which alternatively searches in conjugate directions.

23: Compute the maximum error and identify the worst-case grid point

24: **return** optimal parameters and corresponding maximum relative error

3.3 Two-Exponential Heuristic Correction to R_2 ($R_2/2exp$)

To further suppress the residual error for the very low b/a ratio, i.e., $a > 100$, while preserving compactness, we added a second exponential term of the same shape with parameters C and D , which are fitted with the same method as for A and B used in P_1 . The new formula is:

$$P'_2 = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - [A e^{-B(1-h)} + C e^{-D(1-h)}]}. \quad (18)$$

We determine (A, B, C, D) , again by minimax fitting (15), see Algorithm 1. The fitting for (C, D) was focused on high eccentricities in $\mathcal{D}_2 = \{b = 1, a \in [100, 1000]\}$, while leaving the near-circular regime essentially governed by the first exponential with parameters (A, B) that were also fitted. The fitting was carried out with the constraint that $A + C$ must be constant, which ensures eliminating the known error of P_{R2} (Equation (9)) when $\frac{a}{b} \rightarrow \infty$, i.e., in extremely high eccentricities. This constant can be easily calculated by observing that when $h = 1$ (or $a/b \rightarrow \infty$), i.e., a completely flat ellipse:

$$\frac{P_{R2}}{1 - [A + C]} = 4a. \quad (19)$$

But since in that limit $P_{R2} = \frac{14}{11}\pi a$, we then solve for $[A + C]$ to obtain $A + C = 4.023374941 \times 10^{-4} = S$. The resulting new parameters for P'_2 are:

$$A \approx 3.37528 \times 10^{-4}, \quad B \approx 10.29662, \quad C \approx 6.48093 \times 10^{-5}, \quad D \approx 40.89043.$$

We have included an additional sigmoid factor σ in order to cancel the effect of the binomial of exponential terms when $a \approx b$, i.e., in low eccentricity values:

$$P_2 = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - \sigma [A e^{-B(1-h)} + C e^{-D(1-h)}]}. \quad (20)$$

in such a way that $P_2 \rightarrow P_{R2}$, right there ($h < 0.35$) where the second Ramanujan's formula is highly accurate, i.e., the sigmoid function is used as a continuous step function to switch between Ramanujan II formula P_{R2} and P'_2 . Here, σ is the sigmoid function:

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-60(h-0.35)}} \right) \quad (21)$$

where $h = 0.35$ is the position where the error graph of P'_2 intersects with the error graph of P_{R2} . On the other hand, in the case of the scaling factor for the variable h , based on trial and error experiments, we have found that a value greater than or equal to 60 produces a sufficiently rapid change in the sigmoid function to commute from P_{R2} to P'_2 in $h = 0.35$, when h increases.

The application or absence of the sigmoid function does not alter the maximum relative error reported in this paper. However, it improves the relative error, as a/b tends to 1. Thus, Equation (20) attains:

- The error approaches the error in P_{R2} in the range $\{b = 1, a < 3.42\}$,
- Maximum relative error ≈ 0.57 ppm in the full range $\{b = 1, a \in [1, \infty]\}$.

Although we have obtained a very good result using 2 exponential terms in (1-h), we consider that these functions are too rigid to fit the error curve of P_{R2} . For this reason we explored the option of using powers of (1-h) to make the fit more flexible.

3.4 Effect of Introducing Power Terms in the Exponential Argument

The introduction of powers in the exponential argument, replacing $(1 - h)$ by $(1 - h)^p$, provides a significant increase in the flexibility of the correction term. To understand this effect, consider that the approximation error of P_{R2} can be written as a smooth function of $h \in [0, 1]$:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{true}}(h) = \frac{P_{\text{exact}}(h) - P_{R2}(h)}{P_{\text{exact}}(h)}. \quad (22)$$

This function exhibits a highly non-uniform behavior across the interval, typically characterized by:

- a relatively flat region for small h (low eccentricity),
- a rapidly changing region as $h \rightarrow 1$ (high eccentricity).

When using standard exponential terms of the form

$$e^{-B(1-h)}, \quad (23)$$

the decay rate is fixed and linear in $(1-h)$, which limits the ability of the model to simultaneously approximate both regions.

By introducing a power p , the argument becomes

$$e^{-B(1-h)^p}, \quad (24)$$

which induces a nonlinear reparameterization of the domain. Specifically:

- If $p > 1$, then $(1-h)^p$ compresses values near $h \approx 1$, sharpening the transition and allowing better resolution of high-curvature regions.
- If $p < 1$, then $(1-h)^p$ expands the region near $h \approx 1$, providing additional flexibility to capture slower variations.

From a functional approximation perspective, the mapping

$$t = (1-h)^p \quad (25)$$

acts as a nonlinear change of variables that adapts the basis functions to the geometry of the error curve.

Consequently, the family of functions

$$e^{-B(1-h)^p} \quad (26)$$

is significantly richer than the standard exponential basis, allowing the approximation to better match both the shape and curvature of $\varepsilon_{\text{true}}(h)$.

This added flexibility explains the substantial reduction in the maximum relative error observed when introducing the exponents p , even without increasing the number of exponential terms.

We consider corrections of the form

$$P \approx \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - \varepsilon(h)}, \quad (27)$$

where $\varepsilon(h)$ is constructed as a sum of exponential terms.

3.5 Strong minimax fitting

The Algorithm 2 performs a strong minimax fitting of a sequence of flexible corrected approximations to Ramanujan's second formula, namely P_{F2} , P_{F3} , P_{F4} , and P_{F5} , each defined by an increasing number of exponential terms with powers of $(1-h)$. For a fixed semi-axis b , the method first constructs dense training and validation grids over the interval of a , and precomputes both the exact perimeter via the complete elliptic integral and the baseline approximation P_{R2} . For each model P_{Fk} , the parameters are constrained so that the amplitudes sum to a fixed constant, ensuring exactness at $h = 1$. The fitting problem is formulated as the minimization of the maximum relative error over the training grid. To solve this highly nonconvex problem, a hybrid strategy is employed: an initial global exploration using differential evolution combined with random multi-start sampling, followed by local refinement using Powell's method applied first to a smooth surrogate objective and then to the exact minimax objective. For higher-order models (P_{F4} and P_{F5}), the search is further enhanced by seeding the initial population with perturbed versions of the best solution obtained from the previous model (P_{F3} or P_{F4} , respectively), allowing an efficient continuation in parameter space. The final solution is selected based on its performance on the validation grid, providing a robust estimate of the true maximum relative error.

Algorithm 2 Strong minimax fitting of flexible corrected Ramanujan II approximations (1st part)

Require: fixed $b > 0$, interval $[a_{\min}, a_{\max}]$, training size N_{tr} , validation size N_{val} , fixed sum S , model type $M \in \{F2, F3, F4, F5\}$

Ensure: optimal parameters and validation maximum relative error

1: Construct the training grid

$$a_i^{(\text{tr})} = a_{\min} + \frac{i-1}{N_{\text{tr}}-1}(a_{\max} - a_{\min}), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{tr}}$$

2: Construct the validation grid

$$a_i^{(\text{val})} = a_{\min} + \frac{i-1}{N_{\text{val}}-1}(a_{\max} - a_{\min}), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{val}}$$

3: **for** each point of both grids **do**

4: Compute

$$h = \left(\frac{a-b}{a+b} \right)^2, \quad t = 1-h$$

5: Compute the exact perimeter

$$P(a, b) = 4a E \left(1 - \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 \right)$$

6: Compute Ramanujan II approximation

$$P_{R2}(a, b) = \pi(a+b) \left(1 + \frac{3h}{10 + \sqrt{4-3h}} \right)$$

7: **end for**

8: **if** $M = F2$ **then**

9: Define

$$P_{F2}(a, b) = \frac{P_{R2}(a, b)}{1 - [Ae^{-Bt^q} + Ce^{-Dt^r}]}$$

10: Impose $A + C = S$

11: Parameterize the amplitudes so that $A, C \geq 0$ and $A + C = S$

12: Let θ denote the free parameters of the model

13: **else if** $M = F3$ **then**

14: Define

$$P_{F3}(a, b) = \frac{P_{R2}(a, b)}{1 - [Ae^{-Bt^q} + Ce^{-Dt^r} + Ee^{-Ft^s}]}$$

15: Impose $A + C + E = S$

16: Parameterize the amplitudes so that $A, C, E \geq 0$ and $A + C + E = S$

17: Let θ denote the free parameters of the model

18: **else if** $M = F4$ **then**

19: Define

$$P_{F4}(a, b) = \frac{P_{R2}(a, b)}{1 - [Ae^{-Bt^q} + Ce^{-Dt^r} + Ee^{-Ft^s} + Ge^{-Ht^u}]}$$

20: Impose $A + C + E + G = S$

21: Parameterize the amplitudes so that $A, C, E, G \geq 0$ and $A + C + E + G = S$

22: Let θ denote the free parameters of the model

23: **else**

24: Define

$$P_{F5}(a, b) = \frac{P_{R2}(a, b)}{1 - [Ae^{-Bt^q} + Ce^{-Dt^r} + Ee^{-Ft^s} + Ge^{-Ht^u} + Ie^{-Jt^v}]}$$

25: Impose $A + C + E + G + I = S$

26: Parameterize the amplitudes so that $A, C, E, G, I \geq 0$ and $A + C + E + G + I = S$

27: Let θ denote the free parameters of the model

28: **end if**

29: Define the exact minimax objective on the training grid

$$\Phi(\theta) = \max_i \frac{|P_M(a_i^{(\text{tr})}, b; \theta) - P(a_i^{(\text{tr})}, b)|}{P(a_i^{(\text{tr})}, b)}$$

Algorithm 2 Strong minimax fitting of flexible corrected Ramanujan II approximations (2nd part)

30: Define a smooth surrogate objective by a large- p norm of the relative error
31: Generate several global candidates by differential evolution with different random seeds
32: Generate additional purely random starting points
33: **if** $M = F4$ **then**
34: Build additional seeded starting points from the best available $F3$ solution
35: Keep the previous parameters close to the $F3$ optimum
36: Assign a small initial mass to the new fourth exponential term
37: Apply small random perturbations
38: **else if** $M = F5$ **then**
39: Build additional seeded starting points from the best available $F4$ solution
40: Keep the previous parameters close to the $F4$ optimum
41: Assign a small initial mass to the new fifth exponential term
42: Apply small random perturbations
43: **end if**
44: Merge all candidates into one starting pool
45: Rank the pool using the smooth surrogate objective
46: Keep the best candidates only
47: **for** each candidate θ_j in the starting pool **do**
48: Refine θ_j by Powell's method applied to the smooth surrogate objective
49: Use the obtained point as initialization for Powell's method applied to the exact minimax objective
50: Evaluate the training maximum relative error
51: Evaluate the validation maximum relative error
52: **end for**
53: Select the candidate with the smallest validation maximum relative error
54: Identify the worst-case validation grid point
55: **return** optimal parameters, training maximum relative error, validation maximum relative error, and worst-case point

3.6 Flexible (with powers of $(1 - h)$) Two-Exponential Model: $R2/F2exp$

To increase flexibility, we introduce exponents:

$$P_{F2} = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - (Ae^{-B(1-h)^q} + Ce^{-D(1-h)^r})}. \quad (28)$$

with constraint:

$$A + C = S, \quad \text{where } S = 4.0233749415669598e - 04 \quad \text{from here on.} \quad (29)$$

The fitted constants using Algorithm 2 are:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 1.6242914264570106 \times 10^{-4} & C &= 2.3990835151099492 \times 10^{-4}, \\ B &= 2.1127747251579692 \times 10^1 & D &= 1.0519954055960756 \times 10^1, \\ q &= 9.3255508111834906 \times 10^{-1} & r &= 1.1169090428284505. \end{aligned}$$

The maximum relative error:

$$\max_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{D}} |\varepsilon(P_{F2})| = 0.2 \text{ ppm}, \quad \mathcal{D} = \{b = 1, a \in [1, 10000]\}. \quad (30)$$

3.7 Flexible (with powers of $(1 - h)$) Three-Exponential Model: $R2/F3exp$

Adding a third exponential:

$$P_{F3} = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - (Ae^{-B(1-h)^q} + Ce^{-D(1-h)^r} + Ee^{-F(1-h)^s})}, \quad (31)$$

with constraint:

$$A + C + E = S. \quad (32)$$

The fitted constants using Algorithm 2 are::

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= 3.2704699236212363 \times 10^{-4} & C &= 3.5335850957003023 \times 10^{-5}, \\
E &= 3.9954650837569342 \times 10^{-5} & B &= 1.2891219860454603 \times 10^1, \\
D &= 4.2799551357558165 \times 10^1 & F &= 1.1430650693589627 \times 10^1, \\
q &= 9.9547975928209875 \times 10^{-1} & r &= 9.5254540577122027 \times 10^{-1}, \\
s &= 1.7028129039833189
\end{aligned}$$

The maximum relative error:

$$\max_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{D}} |\varepsilon(P_{F3})| = 0.055 \text{ ppm}, \quad \mathcal{D} = \{b = 1, a \in [1, 10000]\} \quad (33)$$

3.8 Flexible (with powers of $(1 - h)$) Four-Exponential Model: $R2/F4exp$

$$P_{F4} = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - (Ae^{-B(1-h)^q} + Ce^{-D(1-h)^r} + Ee^{-F(1-h)^s} + Ge^{-H(1-h)^u})}, \quad (34)$$

with constraint:

$$A + C + E + G = S. \quad (35)$$

The fitted constants using Algorithm 2 are:

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= 2.9366973637885561 \times 10^{-4} & C &= 6.2926379208842441 \times 10^{-5}, \\
E &= 2.9058024718557447 \times 10^{-5} & G &= 1.6683353850440461 \times 10^{-5}, \\
B &= 1.2794318096403178 \times 10^1 & D &= 3.3874449738045193 \times 10^1, \\
F &= 1.1324362335219835 \times 10^1 & H &= 5.6819551657952999 \times 10^1, \\
q &= 1.0518831146664076 & r &= 1.0185882839340432, \\
s &= 1.7946231875051635 & u &= 8.9334188171605333 \times 10^{-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

The maximum relative error:

$$\max_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{D}} |\varepsilon(P_{F4})| = 0.03 \text{ ppm}, \quad \mathcal{D} = \{b = 1, a \in [1, 10000]\}. \quad (36)$$

3.9 Flexible (with powers of $(1 - h)$) Five-Exponential Model: $R2/F5exp$

$$P_{F5} = \frac{P_{R2}}{1 - (Ae^{-B(1-h)^q} + Ce^{-D(1-h)^r} + Ee^{-F(1-h)^s} + Ge^{-H(1-h)^u} + Ie^{-J(1-h)^v})}, \quad (37)$$

with constraint:

$$A + C + E + G + I = S. \quad (38)$$

The fitted constants using Algorithm 2 are:

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= 2.8343296895393181 \times 10^{-4} & C &= 7.4224722610190177 \times 10^{-5}, \\
E &= 1.7465913309214121 \times 10^{-5} & G &= 2.3676211292968272 \times 10^{-5}, \\
I &= 3.5376779903916304 \times 10^{-6} & B &= 1.2505836332877127 \times 10^1, \\
D &= 3.8348802290432275 \times 10^1 & F &= 1.1947955069812146 \times 10^1, \\
H &= 6.9087704651767510 \times 10^1 & J &= 1.0915293353669674 \times 10^2, \\
q &= 1.0876352435861614 & r &= 1.0965569005811395, \\
s &= 2.0263941926207321 & u &= 9.6710133279772192 \times 10^{-1}, \\
v &= 8.4364533457417601 \times 10^{-1}
\end{aligned}$$

The maximum relative error:

$$\max_{(a,b) \in \mathcal{D}} |\varepsilon(P_{F5})| = 0.0216 \text{ ppm}, \quad \mathcal{D} = \{b = 1, a \in [1, 10000]\} \quad (39)$$

3.10 Observed Structure and Conjectures

The sequence of approximations shows a systematic reduction of the error:

$$0.20 \rightarrow 0.055 \rightarrow 0.03 \rightarrow 0.0216 \text{ ppm.} \quad (40)$$

Reordering the exponential terms by increasing decay rate reveals a consistent structure:

- Two dominant exponentials with decay rates approximately $b \approx 11$ – 13 ,
- One exponent near 1 and another near 2,
- Additional terms forming a rapidly decaying corrective tail.

This suggests the decomposition

$$\varepsilon(h) = \varepsilon_{\text{core}}(h) + \varepsilon_{\text{tail}}(h). \quad (41)$$

We therefore conjecture that the correction admits an expansion of the form

$$\varepsilon(h) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k e^{-b_k(1-h)^{p_k}}, \quad (42)$$

with

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k = S, \quad (43)$$

ensuring exact cancellation of the error at $h = 1$.

These results indicate that Ramanujan’s second formula can be systematically corrected by a structured exponential expansion whose partial sums drive the approximation error arbitrarily close to zero.

4 Numerical Evaluations

4.1 Computational Setup

All experiments used dense meshes, high-precision evaluation of P through numeric evaluation of elliptic integral $E(\cdot)$, and reproducible code.

4.1.1 Setup for Minimax Fitting of $R2/1exp$ and $R2/2exp$

During Minimax fitting, the objective functions are evaluated pointwise on the mesh; In Algorithm 1 $a_{min} = 1$, $a_{max} = 100$ for $R2/1exp$, and $a_{min} = 1$, $a_{max} = 1000$ for $R2/2exp$; finally $N = 3000$. On the other hand, we obtain $R2/1exp$ and $R2/2exp$ as a result of the fitting process. Both Equations (16) and (20) are closed-form single-line formulas that preserve numerical stability and require only elementary operations and one exponential as in Equation (16), or two exponentials and a sigmoidal factor as in Equation (20).

4.1.2 Setup for Strong Minimax Fitting of $R2/F2exp$, $R2/F3exp$, $R2/F4exp$ and $R2/F5exp$

In Algorithm 2 $a_{min} = 1$, $a_{max} = 10000$ and $N = 3000$ for $R2/F2exp$, $R2/F3exp$, $R2/F4exp$ and $R2/F5exp$.

4.1.3 Setup for validations of the formulas

To evaluate the accuracy of the different closed-form approximations, we designed a computational framework in Python using `NumPy`, `mpmath`, and `Matplotlib`. A dense mesh with uniformly distributed dots 10^4 was generated to test the methods in the domain a , setting $b = 1$ and varying $a \in [1.0001, 10,000]$. Due to the restriction $a > b$ of Moscato’s formula, we have used 1.0001 instead of 1.

The exact perimeter of the ellipse was calculated using the complete elliptic integral of the second kind in Equation (1), whose high-precision value serves as a reference benchmark. Each approximation method (20th and 21st centuries): Ramanujan I formula ($R1$), Ramanujan II formula ($R2$), Cantrell, Koshy’s formula (1), Koshy’s formula (2), Moscato and our proposed were then applied to the same mesh. For each method, we evaluated the absolute value of relative error as $|\varepsilon(P^*)|$, respectively. Finally, the maximum absolute value of all relative errors was found. The computational framework for testing all methods are available to anyone in (16).

4.2 Relative Error Comparison (Selected Methods)

Figure 1 shows on a logarithmic scale the absolute relative error for the following six accurate closed-form approximations: Cantrell, Koshy 1, Koshy 2, Moscato, $R2/1exp$ [using the sigmoid factor σ multiplying the constant A of Equation (16)], and $R2/2exp$ (Equation (20)) as a function of a ($a \in [1.0001, 100000]$), while b remains constant and equal to 1. As an illustrative reference, we locate the orbits of three known comets, all with $a < 100$.

Figure 1: Absolute relative error comparison between the following approximations: Cantrell, Koshy 1, Koshy 2, Moscato, $R2/1exp$ [using the sigmoid factor σ], and $R2/2exp$. In addition, we show three references of elliptical orbits of famous comets.

Figure 2 shows on a logarithmic scale the absolute relative error for the flexible formulas: $R2/2exp$, $R2/F2exp$, $R2/F3exp$, $R2/F4exp$ and $R2/F5exp$. They are compared with $R2$ and $Cantrell$ approximations.

Figure 2: Absolute relative error comparison of flexible formulas compared to $R2/2exp$.

4.3 Summary of Maximum Errors

Table 2 summarizes the maximum relative errors and their respective positions in h of modern ellipse perimeter approximations.

Table 2: Locations in h of the maximum relative error of modern ellipse perimeter approximations.

Formula	$h \in [0, 1]$	Absolute Maximum Relative Error (ppm)
Ramanujan I	1	4155.03
Ramanujan II	1	402.337
Cantrell	0.805747	14.4608
Koshy 2	0.469204	9.33774
Koshy 1	0.234143	8.73519
Moscato	0.977093	2.72138
Mamoun (RII+3exp)	0.98	0.083 (reported)
R2/1exp (proposed)	1	40.27
R2/2exp (proposed)	0.748	0.573
R2/F2exp (proposed)	0.716	0.213
R2/F3exp (proposed)	0.751	0.055
R2/F4exp (proposed)	0.327	0.0296
R2/F5exp (proposed)	0.300	0.0217

In our proposed formulas from $R2/2exp$ to $R2/F5exp$ the constraint that the sum of the coefficients of the exponential terms must be equal to S causes the error to decrease from its maximum value to 1.94×10^{-4} ppm (due to the limited precision of S) as the eccentricity increases, reaching the flat ellipse limit when $b/a \rightarrow 0$, or $e \rightarrow 1$, $h \rightarrow 1$.

The reported maximum relative errors correspond to the largest values observed over dense numerical grids covering the domain of interest. Although the sampling is sufficiently fine to capture the error behavior with high confidence, these values should be interpreted as empirical maxima rather than strict global bounds. A formal proof of global optimality or worst-case error bounds is beyond the scope of this work.

5 Discussion

The comparative analysis of maximum relative errors provides a clear picture of the performance of classical and modern closed-form approximations for the ellipse perimeter. The results are summarized in Table 2, and the discussion below highlights both qualitative trends and quantitative comparisons. The earliest formulas, such as Kepler and Euler, offer only rough estimates: their errors grow quickly as the ellipse becomes more eccentric, with deviations exceeding 10%. Ramanujan's contributions mark a significant leap in accuracy: both $R1$ and $R2$ drastically reduce the error, with $R2$ already achieving a maximum relative error of 402 ppm. Later refinements by Cantrell and Koshy succeeded in pushing the error to 14.46 ppm and 8.74 ppm, respectively. The latter reaching an accuracy of sub-10 ppm across most of the tested range. Our first exponential correction to Ramanujan's formula $R2/1exp$ produces a global maximum relative error of 40.27 ppm, but a remarkable result of only 2.14 ppm in the range of $a \in [1, 100]$ while keeping $b = 1$. We used this limited interval ($a \in [1, 100]$) due to its usefulness in covering the range of eccentricities of all known celestial bodies. This suggests that $R2/1exp$ is very useful within that interval. Subsequently, with the aim of further expanding the range of eccentricities for $R2/1exp$, we again fitted the constants from $a = 1$ to $a = 1000$. This time, we obtained a maximum relative error of 7 ppm and a negative growth from $a = 1000$ onward. For this reason, we decided to return to the previous fitting made from $a = 1$ to 100 and which gave an error of 2.14 ppm. In this case, we observed that the relative error as a function of h decreases negatively from $a = 100$ and that this curve also resembles a negative exponential function. Because of this last observation, we decided to add an extra exponential term; that is, we added an exponential term to the first term that already existed in $R2/1exp$. Then, we introduced the constraint $A + C = 4.023374941 \times 10^{-4}$, which guarantees the cancellation of $R2$ error at $h = 1$. Once this constraint was taken into account, we fitted B , C and D from $a = 1$ to 1000 for $R2/2exp$.

$R2/2exp$ is a single-line expression that requires only five exponentiations. To our knowledge, this formulation achieves a lower error observed over the tested grids, which is below 0.58 ppm in the entire range while maintaining minimal computational overhead.

On the other hand, $R2/F3exp$ remains compact, a single line, and with such a low maximum relative error (0.055ppm) that it easily makes it one of the most accurate approximations to the perimeter of the ellipse in the world.

To contextualize the improvement, we compare the maximum relative error of recent methods with the formulas proposed in this paper, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Maximum relative error for all the range of eccentricities ($0 \leq h \leq 1$) of the most accurate perimeter approximations (20th and 21st centuries).

Finally, and as an additional piece of information we have computed Euler-Ivory expansion in Equation (6) and have seen that 148 terms of the series are required to reach a maximum relative error of 0.57 ppm in the same interval $b = 1$, and $a \in [1, 1000]$ that we used for our $R2/2exp$ approximation. And for $R2/F3exp$ 306 terms of that series are required to reach a maximum relative error of 0.055 ppm in the same interval.

6 Conclusions

We summarize the main conclusions as follows:

- Novel compact closed-form approximations for the perimeter of the ellipse have been developed by introducing exponential corrections to Ramanujan’s second formula.
- We have designed a method with exceptional accuracy that simultaneously preserves minimal computational and notational overhead. Specifically, our expressions are closed-form and single-line formulas $R2/1exp$, $R2/2exp$, $R2/F2exp$, $R2/F3exp$, $R2/F4exp$, $R2/F5exp$ that achieve maximum relative error values of approximately 40 ppm, 0.57 ppm, 0.2 ppm, 0.055 ppm, 0.03 ppm, 0.02 ppm, respectively, over dense grids tested covering the full eccentricity range, i.e. $0 \leq h \leq 1$.
- As far as we know, our expressions outperform in accuracy and compactness all other approaches that are currently reported in peer reviewed publications.
- To contextualize the improvement of the proposed approximations, we can, for example, use the specific case of $R2/F3exp$ and $R2/F5exp$; in this paper, we have shown that modern formulas such as Ramanujan II, Cantrell, Koshy I, and Moscato have errors 6700, 241, 145.6 and 45.3 times greater than the error of $R2/F3exp$. And those same formulas have errors 20117, 723, 437 and 136 times greater than the error of our most accurate approximation $R2/F5exp$.
- Likewise, we can conjecture that there exists an infinite series of exponential terms with rapid convergence capable of correcting the error of Ramanujan’s 2nd approximation to the perimeter of the ellipse

References

- [1] Sivagnanam, S.; Kailasapathi, P.; Ramesh Kumar, S. A Multi-band crescent shaped microstrip patch antenna with spiral shape ground slot for UWB applications. *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application and Management*. **2018**, *4*, 489–493.
- [2] Brehl, D. E.; Dow, T. A. Review of vibration-assisted machining. *Precis. Eng.* **2008**, *32*, 153–172.
- [3] Nakka, R.; Kumar, A. P.; Harursampath, D., Ponnusami, S. A. Influence of fibre cross-section profile on the multi-physical properties of uni-directional composites. *Composite structures* **2023**, *321*, 117321.

- [4] Sun, X. Development of an improved thermal model of the human body and an experimental investigation of heat transfer from a moving cylinder. Ph.D. Thesis, Kansas State University, Manhattan, KS, USA, 2012.
- [5] Kepler, J. *Astronomia Nova*; Prague, Czech Republic, 1609. Available online: <https://archive.org/details/Astronomianovaa00Kep1> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [6] Almkvist, G.; Berndt, B. Gauss, Landen, Ramanujan, the arithmetic–geometric mean, ellipses, π , and the Ladies Diary. *Am. Math. Mon.* **1988**, *95*, 585–608.
- [7] Sýkora, J. Approximations of ellipse perimeters and of the Complete Elliptic Integral $E(x)$. Review of known formulae. *Ebyte.it Stan's Library III*, 2005. Available online: <http://www.ebyte.it/library/docs/math05a/EllipsePerimeterApprox05.html> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [8] Kennedy, H.C. *Selected Works of Giuseppe Peano*; University of Toronto Press: Toronto, ON, Canada, 1973. Available online: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.3138/j.ctt1vxmd8x> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [9] Euler, L. *Nova Series Infinita Maxime Convergens Perimetrum Ellipsis Exprimens*; 1774. Available online: <https://scholarlycommons.pacific.edu/euler-works/448> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [10] Michon, G. P. Final answers: Perimeter of an Ellipse. 2007. Available online: <https://www.numericana.com/answer/ellipse.htm> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [11] Ramanujan, S. Modular equations and approximations to π . *Q. J. Math.* **1914**, *45*, 350–372. Available online: <https://ramanujan.sirinudi.org/Volumes/published/ram06.pdf> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [12] Koshy, K.I. Ellipse perimeter approximation: Two high accuracy formulae derived from a perimeter property. *Int. J. Sci. Res. Math. Stat. Sci.* **2024**, *11*, 1–5.
- [13] Moscato, P.; Ciezak, A. A new approximation for the perimeter of an ellipse. *Algorithms* **2024**, *17*, 464. Available online: <https://www.mdpi.com/1999-4893/17/10/464> (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [14] Sýkora, S. Advances in approximations of ellipse perimeters and of the complete elliptic integral. *Stan's Library*, 2007. Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331938805_Advances_in_Approximations_of_Ellipse_Perimeters_and_of_the_Complete_Elliptic_Integral (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [15] Powell, M.J.D. *Approximation Theory and Methods*; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK, 1981.
- [16] Ayala-Raggi, S.E. Ellipse Perimeter Approximation. GitHub Repository, 2026. Available online: https://github.com/sraggi/ellipse_perimeter_approx (accessed on 21 March 2026).
- [17] Mamoun, M. Two Foci, One Cup: Successive World-Record Equations for Ellipse Perimeter. *ResearchGate* **2026**. Available online: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29942.77123> (accessed on 3 April 2026).